

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND CALCULATION METHODS OF ENERGY-SAVING MODES OF AUTOMATED ELECTRICAL VEHICLES

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Abstract: *It is known that about 60 - 70% of the electricity generated in the whole world is consumed by the electric drives of various mechanisms and equipment. Almost 50% of the electricity produced in the world is consumed by alternating current and constant current electrical systems. This article provides information about the theoretical basis and calculation methods of energy-saving modes of the system.*

Key words: *Useful work coefficient, electric motor, drive, Asynchronous electric drive.*

Currently, there are the following main ways to save energy in an automated electric vehicle:

1. By improving the motor selection method according to the real change of the load of the production mechanism, the correct selection of the motor power of the electric drive, because if the motor power is smaller than the load power, the motor will convert energy inefficiently and die when working. the power wasted in the wall and in the transmission line is greatly increased.

2. Replacement of automated electric drive motors of production mechanisms with energy-saving electric motors with increased FIK and power coefficient values due to increase in asset mass (copper and iron);

3. The transition from non-speed-adjustable electric drives to adjustable-speed electric drives allows to save resources (water, heat, etc.) not only in the automated electric drive system, but also in the production mechanism.

4. Development and creation of a special technical solution that ensures the minimum energy requirement in cases where the load is variable in electrical circuits whose speed is not adjustable, as well as in controlled automated electrical circuits due to changes in the coordinates of the electrical circuit according to the requirements of the technological process. Choosing and implementing one of the above ways of energy saving depends on the specific conditions created by the technological mechanism, and each of them has its own advantages and disadvantages. Taking into account the energy crisis and the increase in the prices of energy carriers, the way to save a large part of the required energy due to the improvement of electric traffic control means is of particular importance. A promising way is the fourth way, which allows to save energy by 30-40% due to the improvement of the automatic electric drive control algorithm. Therefore, the main attention should be focused on the theoretical issues and calculation methods of energy-saving automated electric driving due to the fundamental improvement of the control algorithm and the most convenient (optimal) control, which ensures the least energy required, due to the operation of new automated electric driving systems. It is known that the largest consumer of electricity in all countries is mainly alternating current electric vehicles, especially electric vehicles with asynchronous motors, which convert almost half of the electricity produced in the world into mechanical energy. The operation of the main part of these motors with a low load or at values much smaller than the nominal one leads to a significant reduction of FIK and SOSP of the electrical system. This situation greatly affects the excessive consumption of electricity and heat energy in the world. Therefore, as an object of analysis, mainly automated electric drive with asynchronous motor was taken. But it will be useful to consider the methods of optimal management of direct current electrical systems.

For fans, air conditioners, pumps and air drive (resting) and other general industrial mechanisms, which are widely used in all industries and various fields of agriculture, depending on the real load of the mechanism, which is important in the national economy, the number of electrical systems improvement of indicators is carried out

with the help of an electric drive system with high efficiency. An electric drive system with an extremely controlled asynchronous motor includes:

1. asynchronous motor M connected to the output of the thyristor voltage adjuster TKR, the control system of the thyristor adjuster BT, the signal collector adder S;
2. motor voltage measuring transducer K 0'0 ' - the output voltage signal differentiation block (KDB) of this measuring transducer is connected;
3. the electric motor power measurement converter Q 0 '0 ' - the output is connected to the multiplier block (KB);
4. the output of the arithmetic block (AB) is also connected to this block;
5. The output of KB is connected to the differentiating block (QDB);
6. The outputs of the differentiation blocks KDB and QDB are connected to the input of the dividing block (BB), and the output of BB is connected to one of the inputs of S. Reducing the wasted electrical energy when asynchronous electric machines work with a changing load is carried out by adjusting the voltage supplied to the motor stator in the function of load or current.

If the asynchronous electric motor is controlled with the minimum power loss in a wide range of frequency changes, the temperature increase of the motor will be minimum, its absolute value will be slightly smaller than the set value. Therefore, automatically maintaining the optimal value of the magnetic current, which minimizes the loss of electric magnetic power, in turn ensures the minimum heating of the motor and creates conditions for the increase of not only the FIK, but also the useful power reserve in a wide range of frequency changes. .

In the conditions of the current energy crisis, besides the traditional functions of production devices, such as starting, braking, speed and torque adjustment, an additional, but now the most important, function - energy saving function - is loaded. If this important function is implemented, the electric drive system will have high technical-economical and energetic indicators when the load on the shaft of the electric motor changes in a wide range, from pure operation to nominal.

Most machines and mechanisms (fans, pump units, compressors, air drives, etc.) asynchronous electric drives are always under load, static data show that the average load of the connection is about 30 - 60% of the nominal load. is, electric motors will have an average of 1500 working hours per year. Failure to use the full capacity of the motor or unreasonable increase of the power of the connection, as well as the operation of the electric motor with low load during additional operations, will lead to a significant decrease in the energy performance of the electric vehicle.

The operation of asynchronous electric drives with low load of the production mechanisms leads to the failure to fully use the installed power of the connection, the unjustified excess consumption of the active and especially reactive power required by the motor, the reduction of the energy efficiency of the device, and the increase of the electric energy consumed per unit of the produced product. In order to effectively use the installed capacity of an asynchronous motor electric drive and to improve the energy performance of the connection, as well as to eliminate (reduce) the unnecessary excess consumption of the power required by the electric motor, widely used asynchronous electric drives without adjustable speed, whose speed is adjustable with frequency A new energy-saving controller for automated electric drive and asynchronous-valve cascades is proposed. Offers are protected by "know-how", copyright certificates and patents of Russia and Uzbekistan.

General industrial energy-saving asynchronous electric drive An asynchronous electric drive with an energy-saving controller works in the following order. A task signal U_{top} is given to the first input of adder 4 (in this case, the adjustable voltage of alternating current) during the startup of asynchronous motor 1, since the mode of operation with the minimum electric current is not provided, the memory block 5 is in a closed state and the input of thyristor control unit 3 is supplied with the $U_b = U_{top}$ signal from the output of accumulator 4. This corresponds to the formation of the maximum value of the voltage U_{max} in the unit 2 of power thyristors, which is equal to the nominal voltage of the motor 1.

Preparation of an experimental sample of an energy-saving controller asynchronous electric drive:

A mock-up of an asynchronous electric drive controlled by an energy-saving controller with a capacity of up to 30 kW in optocouplers and 160 kW in thyristors was prepared to control a short-circuited rotor asynchronous motor. The controller is assembled on the basis of the elements produced in the CIS enterprises, the dimensions of the energy-saving block are 150x150x100 mm, the power is 30 kW, if necessary, the power is 500 kW and more, according to the customer's request. can be prepared. The energy-saving controller provides a number of the following functions:

- depending on the load value, the value of the stator winding voltage changes with the optimization of the stator current;
- smooth change of voltage from zero to nominal at start-up;
- protect the electric motor by disconnecting it from the network;
- if one of the phases is disconnected by the mains supply network and by the motor,
- notification that the protection has worked, that there is a provision in each phase;
- limiting the starting current of the electric motor (1 - 7) in the adjustment range IN;
- the ability to reset the operation of protective devices

The use of the controller is most effective in motor drives with 0 variable loads and small loads.

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